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TAXIS REPRESENTATION IN DIFFERENT SYSTEMS LANGUAGES

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Аннотация: Мақолада қардош бўлмаган турли тизимли тилларда таксис категорияси ифода-планининг турфа хил моделлари таҳлил қилинади. Унда таксис семантикасининг ўзбек, инглиз ва рус тиллари морфологияси конверб тизимлари орқали воқеланиши ёритилган. Хусусан, сифатдош, герундий ва айрим бошқа феълнинг функционал шакллари таҳлил натижалари инглиз, ўзбек ҳамда рус тиллари материали мисолида қиёсий ўрганилган фактлар асосида тақдим қилинган.

Калит сўзлар: таксис, категория, модел, муносабат, морфологик, ифода-план, конверб, равишдош, нофинит, сифатдош I-II.

Аннотация: В статье анализируются различные модели план-выражения категории таксиса в разных системных языках, не связанных друг с другом. Описана реализация семантики таксиса через морфологию конвербальных систем узбекского, английского и русского языков. В частности, представлены результаты анализа функциональных форм прилагательного, герундия и некоторых других глаголов на основе сравнительных фактов на примере материалов английского, узбекского и русского языков.

Ключевые слова: таксис, категория, модель, отношение, морфологический, план-выражение, конверб, деепричастие, нефинитный, причастие I-II.

Absrtact: The article analyzes various models of plan-expression of the category of taxis in different system languages that are not related to each other. The implementation of taxis semantics through the morphology of converbal systems of the

Uzbek, English and Russian languages is described. In particular, the results of the analysis of the functional forms of the adjective, gerund and some other functional verbs are presented based on comparative facts involving the example of materials from the English, Uzbek and Russian languages.

Keywords: taxis, category, model, relation, morphological, expression-plan, converb, adverbial participle, non-finite, participle I-II.

INTRODUCTION

In the languages of the world, there are two main models of taxis expression in verbal systems: non-finite and combined [Plungyan, 2000].

In the first model, taxis relations are expressed by specialized verbal forms such as Russian gerunds. They do not have absolute time values and are syntactically dependent on the main predicate, which expresses absolute time. It is believed that such dependent taxis forms are either adjective (i.e. “participles”) or adverbial (i.e. “adverbial participle”). The non-finite model is considered characteristic of Russian and other Slavic languages (where the perfect gerund participle is used to express precedence, and the imperfect gerund participle is used to express simultaneity), as well as Altaic, Uralic, Turkic, Dagestan and, including, Uzbek languages. That is, according to existing ideas, the Uzbek and Russian languages belong to the same type of the so-called “adverbial participle operating languages”.

English can be placed somewhere between these two languages in the taxicity scale, despite the fact that, according to some researchers, it represents the second (combined) taxis model. The combined taxis model is considered one of the most striking features of the verbal systems of the Romance, Germanic, and Bulgarian languages. Such a taxis model is characterized by the fact that grammemes of both relative and absolute time are simultaneously expressed in verb forms. Such forms have also received special names, for example, pluperfect expresses precedence in the past, imperfect - simultaneity in the past relative to the moment of speech.

We refer the Uzbek language to the so-called “taxis-relevant languages” [Isarov, 2020]. English occupies an intermediate position. This location on the taxicity scale is

due to the fact that the meanings of dependent taxis are widely represented in constructions with non-finite verb forms in both languages. But at the same time, the taxis convertibles of the compared languages differ significantly in qualitative terms.

THEORETICAL BASIS

Taxis relations are limited to the framework of the statement/utterance. This refers to statements equal to a sentence or a superphrasal unity [see Bondarko, 1984: 74].

The description of the taxis in the form of a functional-semantic field (FSF) harmoniously combines the form-centric approach with the functional-semantic one. The construction of the FSF of a certain functional-semantic category (FSC) involves the description of all means of its expression and the establishment of their hierarchy - the core and the periphery. The morphological grammatical category can act as the core of the FSF. The description of such a grammatical category using the form-centric approach is part of the construction of the FSF in the implementation of the functional-semantic approach.

Taxis meanings are intentional in essence. They refer to the level of the speaker's speech tactics and are realized in speech as actual elements of the expressed and perceived meaning about the temporal contingency of actions [Semyonova, 2004].

The semantic basis of taxis predetermines the possibility of updating its meanings with the help of language means of different nature, not only within the framework of syntactic polypredicative constructions, but also within the verb lexeme. Polypredicateness is only a particular, explicit, condition for the realization of taxis. Its other condition - implicit - is represented by event verbs of polypropitive semantics (multiplicatives and distributions), which include categorical signs of taxis in their content structure. A polypredicative complex is understood as: a) combinations of primary and secondary predication in constructions with gerunds (as well as participles and other non-finite verbal forms); b) different types of polypredication in complex sentences and sentences with homogeneous predicates.

The grammatical core of the FSF of taxis in the Uzbek language is the inflectional paradigm of taxis convertibles. The allomorphic means of representing taxis relations

to such convertibles are constructions of subordinate clauses of the Russian language, constructions with forms of relative tenses, and tense coordination in English. FSC has a universal, interlingual nature, and FSF, which are a set of linguistic means of a particular language, as a rule, are allomorphic in relation to universal semantic categories. The semantic features of FSC of taxis, like other FSCs, can receive allomorphic expression within the same language and, moreover, in languages of different genetic and typological classes. And in languages of different structural types, the very nature of the distribution of semantic features of the FSC of taxis between language levels may differ. Taxis relations, expressed mainly by syntactic means in Russian and English, in the Uzbek language are formalized by means of morphology, therefore, the system of complex sentences is not characteristic of the latter. This makes interesting, from the point of view of taxis typology, a contrastive and universal-typological study of taxis expression forms in languages of different systems, especially those that are genetically and typologically distant. Such a study provides observations on the degree of grammaticalization of taxis in the compared languages, on the nomenclature of taxis meanings and ways of their linguistic expression. The features of allomorphy in the manifestations of the category of taxis in the compared languages can be isomorphic in these languages with other languages.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the Uzbek language, the center of the “precedence” microfield is non-morphological elements, while in English it is the morphological category of temporal reference (Perfect).

Observations about the specifics of the manifestation of FSC taxis in the compared languages are of considerable interest for the development of the theory and typology of the grammatical category under discussion. The significance of such observations is due to the fact that these languages present a type of morphological grammatical category of taxis that has not previously attracted sufficient attention.

Taxis is always a relation: expressed in the utterance, primarily with the help of verb-predicative forms, a temporary relation within the framework of an integral time

period [Protsko, 1989]. Speaking about the priority of verbal predicates in the actualization of taxis semantics, it should be noted that the categorical meanings of other components of the polypredicative complex turn out to be no less relevant for its expression [Semenova, 2000].

Taxis relations, according to some researchers, are also marked by nouns with event semantics: Дардан сўнг қайтдим – I returned after classes – Возвратился после урока **cf.** Дарс тамомлангач қайтдим – I returned after classes had finished – Возвратился после того, как закончился урок. A number of authors highlight taxis relations between participles and personal verbs: Берига келувчи вагон кўринди – Стал виден вагон, идущий сюда. A number of authors, including us, distinguish taxis relations between participles and personal verbs: Стал виден вагон, идущий сюда.

The most widely used means of expressing taxis meanings in English is the present participle. Constructions with Participle I are able to convey different types of taxi relations. They are a productive means of expressing the meaning of simultaneity. The perfect forms of Participle I express the meanings of precedence. In cases where the participle is used in a sentence after the support form, the following meanings are realized. A comparison of varieties of taxis constructions in English and Uzbek shows that the Uzbek language expresses taxis mainly by morphological inflectional forms of the verb. The English language expresses taxis semantics mainly by syntactic constructions with invariable verbal forms of participles I and II, and gerunds:

Having collected all the material, he wrote a full report on the work of the commission // **After collecting** all the material, he wrote a full report on the work of the commission // **After** he **had collected** all the material, he wrote a full report on the work of the commission;

Having been dried and sorted the goods were placed in the warehouse // **After** the goods **had been dried and sorted** they were placed in the warehouse.

In English, the dependent situation preceding the main situation is denoted in allomorphic ways: **Arriving** to the station we **went** straight to the booking office –

Вокзалга **келгач**, тўғри кассага **бордик**; **When we arrived** to the station we **went** straight to the booking office – Вокзалга **келган пайтимизда**, тўғри кассага **бордик**.

In the first, simple sentence, the “arriving” converb is used, in the complex sentence, the same ratio is conveyed by the “when arrived” construction.

Participial, gerundial constructions and complex sentences with clauses of time in English are allomorphic means of expressing a dependent taxis, because participle and gerund phrases are easily transformed into complex sentences. Dependent predicates of taxis constructions with subordinate clauses of time are combinations of finite verb forms with a conjunction.

Objects (adverbial participle, participles, homogeneous predicates and complex sentences) that came into the field of view of taxis theory were simultaneously considered in other aspects and in other terms.

Elements of taxis semantics are also found in the content structure of prefix verbs expressing the idea of a retrospective action such as “reread a book, rebuild a house”, etc. When they are used, one action is actually indicated, while the second, correlative, constitutes the presuppositional part of the content of the statement, i.e. is implied by the “general knowledge fund” that is in the subtext [Semenova, 2000].

Vocabulary and grammar are not the only means that the language uses to denote undifferentiated taxis. Syntax is also involved very actively. Thus, the most common structural type of sentence, where the taxis type of meanings under consideration is actualized, is sentences with homogeneous predicates. If sentences with homogeneous predicates act as one of the predicative units of a complex sentence, then the taxis relation becomes more complicated (“double taxis relations”), and the probability of its undifferentiated interpretation increases significantly [Maksimova, 2005].

The taxis constructions of the English language, in which the dependent action is expressed in a non-finite verb form, can be easily transformed into complex sentences. That is, taxis relations, transmitted in English by the subordinate parts of complex sentences, are functionally equivalent to the taxis converts of the Uzbek language correlated with them. Taxis convertibles of the Uzbek language and subordinate

clauses of tense and conditionalities of the English language are, as shown by the comparison, language forms that are allomorphic with respect to the units of the content plan, which are the same for both languages.

CONCLUSION

So, taxis relations in the languages under consideration can be expressed by different means: with the help of specialized non-finite and finite forms, and with the help of conjunctions in conjunction with non-specialized finite verb forms, and with the help of prepositions in conjunction with non-specialized verb forms, verbal nouns, as well as with non-verbal predicate substantives.

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